

MODELING AND SIMULATION OF NON-ISOTHERMAL REACTIVE RESIN FLOW IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING

Pavel Simacek^{1*} And Suresh G. Advani¹

¹Center for Composite Materials and Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware (*Corresponding Author: psimacek@udel.edu)

Keywords: *Composite-Materials, Liquid Composite Molding, Flow Modeling, Numerical Simulation*

1. Introduction

In Liquid Composite Molding (LCM), fibrous reinforcing preforms are placed in a mold and infused with thermoset resin. Once the reinforcement is saturated and the resin cures, the part is demolded. The resin infusion should fully saturate the preform for acceptable mechanical properties. Entrapped dry spots are detrimental to part performance and may require either repairs or result in scraping of the part. To ensure successful filling, numerical analysis of the flow process has been widely applied.

The numerical simulation of resin flow in LCM has been around for more than two decades [1-5]. The modeling provides the resin flow patterns and helps to determine the pressure or time necessary for infusion. Advanced applications of simulation include process optimization and control [6-8]. Note that these applications generally place larger requirements on model computational performance rather than on absolute accuracy. Consequently, the model usually assumes isothermal and constant viscosity resin flow in rigid porous media.

There may still be need to include additional physics that is usually neglected, as it might be significant for particular cases - such as dual scale flow, acceleration (gravity) forces and fabric deformation [9-11]. The variable temperature and/or resin reaction may become very significant and has been addressed [4, 12-13]. As these generalizations come at a significant cost in both computational performance and material characterization, we will examine the latter ones in some detail.

The mathematical model describes the volume averaged flow velocity $\langle v_f \rangle$ by Darcy's law to relate it to the resin pressure p gradient through preform

permeability tensor, \mathbf{K} , and resin viscosity η as shown below:

$$\langle v_f \rangle = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} \cdot \nabla p \quad (1)$$

Governing equation is then obtained using mass conservation in filled domain and solved quasi-statically to obtain resin pressure field at any instant.

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} \cdot \nabla p \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The solution domain changes with time. The flow front is advanced, either after the pressure is solved (explicitly) from (2) or during the solution step (implicitly). Then, the process is repeated until the mold is filled or when resin reaches the vent location.

The local temperature and resin reaction enter this equation through a single term, the resin viscosity η . The viscosity may strongly depend on both the temperature and the degree of cure. Thus, for such cases one needs to evaluate two additional, non-linear equations throughout the solution domain, (i) for the degree of cure, α , and (ii) temperature, T . This additionally requires one to provide thermal and reaction material parameters.

The energy equation,

$$(\rho c_p)_{ef} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\rho c_p)_f \langle v_f \rangle \cdot \nabla T = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{K}_D) \cdot \nabla T + \eta \langle v_f \rangle \cdot \mathbf{K}^{-1} \cdot \langle v_f \rangle + \phi R \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

balances the change in internal energy and heat convection with heat conduction and dispersion, dissipation and heat generation due to the chemical reaction. One needs to provide porosity ϕ , the effective fluid (resin) density and heat capacity $((\rho c_p)_{ef}$, the fluid(resin) density and heat capacity $(\rho c_p)_f$, heat conductivity and dispersion

tensors respectively (\mathbf{k} and \mathbf{K}_D), heat of reaction R and the reaction rate $\partial\alpha/\partial t$. The reaction equation presents the species preservation in the form:

$$\phi \frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial t} + \langle v_f \rangle \cdot \nabla\alpha = \nabla \cdot \phi(\mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}_D) \cdot \nabla\alpha + \phi \dot{R}_\alpha \quad (4)$$

Note that, besides of reaction rate \dot{R}_α one needs to specify the diffusion tensor \mathbf{D} which also has the dispersion component. In non-isothermal reactive case, equations (3) and (4) should be solved coupled with the equation (2) to provide proper viscosity value for movement of the resin flow front. The full model extension raises two issues. One, the problem to solve is growing in size and complexity. Second, we are boldly using material data that may not be actually available or that are at least difficult to determine reliably. In this light, one should ask two questions. First, is it possible to simplify the model of reactive resin flow to obtain efficient simulation tool, and when is such a simplification feasible. Second, what can be gained by modeling the non-isothermal process in its entire complexity?

2. Reactive resins without significant exotherm or external heating

Assume that the boundary and initial conditions are isothermal, as will be very common and realistic case. The resin may continue to cure and generate heat during the infusion. This will influence the viscosity, sometimes considerably even for very small conversion degrees. The equations (3) and (4) may be, however, used to judge whether the temperature will become non-uniform and the non-isothermal solution will be needed. If no significant heat is generated during the reaction, the equations can be solved directly for constant temperature and transient $\alpha(t)$ with no spatial dependence, assuming the resin is pre-mixed and reacts similarly in all locations.

The expanded description is obviously still applicable. Nonetheless, (3) and (4) have the trivial solution mentioned above and it can provide the analyst with far more efficient alternative. Characterizing viscosity (instead of the reaction rates and other parameters), one can obtain an explicit relation $\eta = \eta(t)$. Since Eq. (2) is solved for pressure under quasi-steady state assumptions, the

solution can be performed just as in the isothermal case. Depending on the boundary conditions applied, the solution may be actually obtained with pre-set viscosity and consequently, the time or pressure can be scaled. Thus, simulation code written for *isothermal* solution could be efficiently used to address the change in viscosity with cure without addressing the change in temperature of the resin.

Fig. 1 Flow chart to model the reacting resin infusion using constant viscosity/temperature solver.

The algorithm utilizing isothermal LIMS simulation package [15] is shown follows (Fig. 1). The flow within system is solved with constant initial viscosity η_0 . This allows the incremental solver to solve the problem very efficiently. After each step, depending on boundary conditions, proper values are adjusted for the different viscosity $\eta(t)$ at the current time t . For constant pressure infusion, the time step size is scaled by the ratio of current viscosity over the initial one $\eta(t)/\eta_0$. For constant flow rate, only the pressure values (if they are recorded at all) must be scaled by $\eta(t)/\eta_0$.

For such cases, the incremental solver preserves the efficiency of the isothermal, constant viscosity approach. For mixed boundary conditions the condition itself has to be modified, as it includes the viscous losses within the injection hardware, and the efficiency would be lost as the equation system would need to be re-assembled with each step. However, it is generally better to model the tubing using one dimensional elements [15] and this case can be easily avoided. For the same reason the direct modification of viscosity with each step - although feasible - should be avoided, at least within LIMS.

Fig. 2 Example infusion into a panel with inserts.

The preserved efficiency allows fast solution of complex flow problems as shown in the Fig. 2 and 3. Two structural layers of preform are separated by inserted tiles and the whole system is infused. This is a complex problem which requires over 40,000 degrees of freedom to capture the variations of flow field (Fig.3), but even with the variable viscosity adjustments at each time step, the filling simulation can be completed within 10-20 minutes on a PC, allowing some optimization of tile layout or other parameters. The filling patterns do not change when transient viscosity is used, but the time scale shifts considerably.

Fig. 3: Infusion simulation into the panel with inserts and polyurea resin with variable viscosity.

In this case, as the reaction model does not introduce any true performance penalty relative to the isothermal model, it can be obviously applied whenever

one knows the transient viscosity, even if the change is insignificant.

3. Full Non-isothermal Model

To solve the system (2)-(4), Two tiered approach was chosen (Fig. 4). The resin pressure and flow progression are solved in quasi-steady approach as in the isothermal case [15], with the difference being that the resin viscosity is now spatially varying with known cure and temperature. Much of the isothermal code is reused in this step. The system solution is still provided by the direct Choleski decomposition.

Fig. 4: Approach to Full Non-Isothermal Modelling.

Next, the temperature and cure development are solved from (3) and (4), utilizing Discontinuous Galerkin Method for spatial discretization. The transient integration is accomplished by TVD-RK3 routine [16].

The implementation allows to solve for developing temperature field *before* the infusion starts (meaning convective transfer in preform only) and both temperature and cure field *after* the infusion is finished, with or without resin flow through the vent (bleeding) after the filling is complete. This allows for interfacing with software analyzing residual stresses due to thermal and cure shrinkage.

The computational requirement of this approach is far higher than the iso-thermal case, as the incremental decomposition can no longer be used, making the Choleski method very inefficient as the order increases from N^2 to N^3 .

4. Non-Isothermal Example

Having developed the non-isothermal solver we may address the second question: Does the non-uniform temperature and cure significantly change the infusion parameters?

To demonstrate this, we implement the common practice of preheated resin infusion into a long panel with a core, as shown in Fig. 5. This problem cannot be obviously simplified as discussed in Section 2, as the temperature within the system varies by at least 40^o C.

The infusion into parts with inserts is complex even in isothermal cases because of merging flow fronts. In this case, this is compounded by temperature variation (we are infusing preheated, on-line mixed resin) and non-symmetric temperature boundary conditions. The metal tool will be kept at room temperature while the core and bagged upper surface have low heat transfer coefficients and can be assumed insulated. Preform is glass fabric, with the permeability and porosity as listed in the figure. Part dimensions are provided in the figure, resin model used was for “well characterized polyester resin” as given in [13].

Fig. 5: Non-isothermal infusion of a panel with foam core: Geometry and material parameters and imposed boundary conditions.

First, we model the infusion with isothermal model (Fig. 6). Flow patterns show that there is no issue with merging flows – as top branch is only slightly

longer than the bottom one – and the remote top corner is the last region to fill, where vent should be placed.

Fig. 6: Isothermal infusion into a panel with core: Flow Patterns.

This result is compared to the non-isothermal flow (Fig. 5) with reacting resin [13]. The flow-fronts are shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 7: Non-isothermal infusion into a panel with core: Flow Patterns.

The change in flow patterns is fairly significant: the flow now progresses faster in the upper branch and the last spot where resin arrives is at the bottom, suggesting different venting location than the isothermal model. To understand this change, we can look at temperature and cure results (Fig. 8).

The tool surface is cooler than the upper insulated surface and hence the temperature in the upper branch is higher which reduces the resin viscosity and consequently makes the resin flow faster. The cure field follows the temperature, with the higher conversion rate in the upper branch. In this case, the conversion rate at the end is still too low (0.05%) to modify the viscosity. Should the reaction reach higher values, its influence may actually reverse the temperature effect on viscosity and flow as the cure increases the viscosity.

Fig. 8: Non-isothermal infusion into a panel with core:
Temperature (top) and Cure (Degree of conversion)
Fields at the end of the infusion..

Phenomena like this cannot be described using isothermal flow or some approximation. Consequently, in the cases where the temperature within the system varies greatly, non-isothermal modeling is necessary.

5. Conclusions

The resin flow modeling can be extended to fully model the non-isothermal infusion of reacting resins into fibrous preforms. The model can then simulate the temperature and cure development before and after infusion as well, as the only difference in governing equations is the absence of convective terms.

As demonstrated above, there are infusion scenarios in which full temperature and cure solution is imperative. In those cases, the solution is available and the largest obstacle to its application may actually be in the resin characterization.

In the case of flow modeling, as in many others, the application of more complex models leads to the deterioration of the computational efficiency and to requirements for additional material characterization. For example, the general description of the resin infusion flow of reacting resin requires solution of coupled system of equations; the mass conservation equation for

pressure, energy equation for temperature and species conservation for degree of conversion. The system is non-linear and coupled. It also requires additional material parameters that are not commonly available. Consequently, the cost of solution is much higher than for the isothermal, non-reacting cases. This may particularly hamper our ability to use simulations for process optimization and control.

As demonstrated above, in special cases, the general solution may be replaced by an equally good simplified one. Therefore, it is imperative to develop good understanding of process physics and use the solution that provides the necessary predictive capability at minimal cost.

Acknowledgement

Research was sponsored by the Army Research Laboratory and was accomplished under Cooperative Agreement Number W911NF-08-2-062. The views and conclusions contained in this document are those of the authors and should not be interpreted as representing the official policies, either expressed or implied, of the Army Research Laboratory or the U.S. Government. The U.S. Government is authorized to reproduce and distribute reprints for Government purposes notwithstanding any copyright notation herein.

The authors would also like to thank Prof. Wook Ryo Hwang of the School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at Gyeongsang National University for his significant help with the non-isothermal problem solver for LIMS.

References

- [1] C.A. Hieber and S.F. Shen. A finite element/finite difference simulation of the injection mold filling process. *J. Non-Newtonian Fluid Mech.*, 7, p. 1-31, 1980.
- [2] M. Bruschke and S.G. Advani. Finite Element/Control Volume Approach to Mold Filling in Anisotropic Porous Media. *Polymer Composites*, 11, p. 398-405, 1990.
- [3] V.R. Voller and Y.F. Chen. Prediction of Filling Times of Porous Cavities. *International Journal Numerical Methods*, v 23, n 7, p. 661-672, 1996.
- [4] F. Trochu, R. Gauvin, and D.-M. Gao. Numerical Analysis of the Resin Transfer Molding Process by

- the Finite Element Method. *Advances in Polymer Technology*, v 12, n 4, p. 329-342, 1993.
- [5] F.R. Phelan. Simulation of the Injection Process in Resin Transfer Molding. Process. *Polymer Composites*, 18, p. 460-476, 1997.
- [6] R. Mathur, B.K. Fink and S.G. Advani. Use of Genetic Algorithms to Optimize Gate and Vent Locations for the Resin Transfer Molding Process. *Polymer Composites 2*, p. 167-178, 1999.
- [7] B. Minaie, Y.F., Chen and M.A. Mescher. A Methodology to Obtain a Desired Pattern During Resin Transfer Molding. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 14, p. 1677-1692, 2002.
- [8] D.R. Nielsen and R. Pitchumani. Closed-loop Flow Control in Resin Transfer Molding Using Real-time Numerical Process Simulation. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2, p. 283-298, 2002.
- [9] P. Simacek, and S.G. Advani. A numerical model to predict fiber tow saturation during liquid composite molding. *Composites Science and Technology*, 63: p. 1725-1736, 2003.
- [10] P. Simacek and S.G. Advani. Role of acceleration forces in numerical simulation of mold filling processes in fibrous porous media. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, v 37, n 11, p 1970-1982, 2006.
- [11] N.C. Correia, F. Robitaille, A.C. Long, C.D. Rudd, P. Šimáček and S.G. Advani. Analysis of the vacuum infusion moulding process: I. Analytical formulation. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, v 36, n 12, p. 1645-1656, 2005.
- [12] N.G. Ngo, R.V. Mohan, P.W. Chung and K.K. Tamma. Recent Developments Encompassing Non-Isothermal/Isothermal Liquid Composite Molding Process Modeling/Analysis: Physically Accurate, Computationally Effective, and Affordable Simulations and Validations. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 6, p. 493-532, 1998.
- [13] M.V. Brusckke and S.G. Advani. A Numerical Approach to Model Non-isothermal, Viscous Flow with Free Surfaces through Fibrous Media. *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Fluids* 19, 1994.
- [14] P. Simacek, D. Heider, J.W. Gillespie Jr. and S.G. Advani. Post-filling flow in vacuum assisted resin transfer molding processes: Theoretical analysis. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, v 40, n 6-7, p. 913-924, 2009.
- [15] P. Simacek and S.G. Advani. Desirable Features in Mold Filling Simulations for Liquid Molding Processes. *Polymer Composites*, 25, p. 355-367, 2004.
- [16] See Jo Kim and Wook Ryol Hwang, Direct numerical simulations of droplet emulsions in sliding bi-periodic frames using the level-set method, *Journal of Computational Physics*, v 225, n 1, p 615-34, 2007.